

Factors of ERP Implementation Failure in the RAK Government

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Abstract:

The implementation factor of the Enterprise Resource Planning system in the RAK government is the biggest challenge for the end-user and the management. Adaptation of the system involves addressing critical success and issues factors. However, relevant literature offers a limited understanding of the system concept. Therefore, the study investigates the essential factors of ERP implementation in the RAK Government to address the issue and help the senior management and government departments resolve and improve the implementation process.

Keywords: ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning), RAK Government, End-user.

Introduction

The study aims to evaluate and analyze the RAK Government's factors.I encountered this during implementing the ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system.The report is based on describing the understanding that contributes towards the implementation of ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) failures in the services of the RAK government, UAE. Therefore, the report helps manage the services based on international perspectives. The failure to implement ERP defines the factors that can define the critical role in managing measured services. The failures are seen in the services of software management that can enable organizations the management of business activities and manufacture marketing processes efficiently (Bala, Kumar &Nadeem, 2019). The services are integrated towards managing functions and facilities used for managing a single system and describing the organization's particular needs and management. The initial costs of implementation define the process of efficient ERP that manages the higher return of investment and various services in the organizations.

Therefore, the implementation of the ERP defines the widespread services and failures for the Services as using inefficient management. The services are seen in managing the latter part in the 90th and 20th century in the services of RAK. The practical implementation of the ERP can enable organizations to manage customization services better. It offers services to the customers that can improve the process and consider cross-departmental coordination in the industry. The implementation

of the factors for the failure of the ERP implementation defines the agreement amongst the end-users. It considers the essential process towards the unique management of the contributing factors in the industry. RAK government works to manage the ERP in the companies and defines the world as presenting the glittering services in the Middle Eastern processes of the government sector. The use of the inspiring pursuit defines the excellence and innovation that effectively manage the financial services and the possible economic landscape for maximum value. It defines the improvement of efficiency as defining possible services.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

Several factors directly affect the implementation of an ERP system in the RAK Government and have not yet been fully identified and addressed. This study aimed to point out, examine, and scrutinize the factors affecting the implementation of the ERP system. Therefore, the data collection and analysis results resulted in a proposal that can help RAK Government senior management come up with a better decision for any other ERP implementation in the future. Some expected changes can define the structure and use the factors explaining failures in implementing ERP. A business process can use the reengineering services to introduce the desired results and expectations towards ERP. Some activities are used in the management of the RAK government for the ERP and management services as using the utility and examining

the cost management analysis. Some ERP packages can define the organization's needs and use the services suited. It is selected as using the required modules. Problems may arise in considering the implementation and defining the ERP processes as the necessary hardware and network services installed for the ERP package's selected management (Tamimi& Mohammad, 2018). Some interlinking processes can use production planning and material management services. It helps manage the control and describes efficiency in the information related to quantity management, where the factors define inefficient resources in capacity management and production facility services. There are some shortages for defining the excess direction of the governmental services that can use declining revenue.

1.2 Implication of the Study

To aid the RAK Government senior management in obtaining a better understanding of the factors that could intercept the successful implementation of any other future ERP system. The senior management can benefit from this study by discovering factors of implementation failures and avoiding them by modifying the strategy based on the recommendation of this study.

1.3 Research Objectives

A survey of the RAK Government senior management, department heads, and end users involved in the implementation was the methodology of this research study. This survey is designed to accomplish three purposes. The first purpose of this survey was to identify critical factors and issues experienced by the RAK Government during and after the implementation process. This survey's second purpose was to determine if the senior management had supported the implementation team. The third purpose of this survey was to determine if the end-users involved were effectively trained to handle the specific access granted as per the implementation plan authority matrix. Other objectives of the survey:

- To define the factors that can implement failures in the ERP services of the RAK government.

- To determine the benefits of the factors and implementation processes.
- To define the incident and incidents in the failure of ERP implementation.
- To understand the factors of ERP implementation that can meet functional requirements and training processes in the RAK management.
- To provide the level of awareness in ERP indicators that can use higher management of RAK businesses.

1.4 Research Assumptions

They assumed that the RAK Government department entities handled different services and authorities and followed the same ERP financial and operation system standard to relate and answer the same research survey questionnaires. Also, it assumed that each survey participant from each government entity answered the questionnaire honestly and based on their implementation experience.

1.5 Design/ Methodology:

This study used a quantitative research methodology. The personnel target of this methodology were the ten senior management and twenty-six SAP end-users from RAK Government department entities (Sheikh Saud bin Saqr Al Qasimi Foundation for Policy Research, RAKGas LLC, RAK-Department of Finance, RAKBANK, RAK- Investment and Development Office, RAK-Sheikh Saqr Program for Government Excellence, RAK- Human Resources, RAK- Electronics and Government Authority, Human Resources Municipality Economic Government, and RAK Government and Excellence Award)

1.6 Limitation of Study:

This study is limited to only the Government of Ras Al Khaimah personnel who are ERP-SAP users.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Brief History Of ERB

Due to the constantly changing work environment, it has become an institution, company, and institution. It has to improve business processes and is referred to as Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) systems. According to Jacobs and Weston Jr. (2007), (Jr.b, 2007), they said that these systems (ERP systems appeared in the early nineties and reached the peak of growth of these systems after the year 200 because institutions needed systems that fully integrated their functions, which were known as "software packages that allow the integration of data intended for transactions and business processes in all The goal of all ERP systems is

ERP Systems Characteristics & Benefits

Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are one of the essential features for which it is famous, which qualifies to have full adoption of essential business solutions in institutions that it has a system that covers all aspects of business, and that can be easily accessed and shared between departments, other institutions and one of the benefits of these systems is that it is a group of systems integrated with one system to facilitate decision-making and reduce costs (Light, 1999). Enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems are one of the essential features for which it is famous. This qualifies it to fully adopt essential business solutions in institutions with a system that covers all aspects of commercial business, which can be easily accessed and shared between departments and other

institutions. One of the benefits of these systems is that it is a group of systems integrated into one system to facilitate the taking decision and cost reduction.

According to (Davenport, 1998), there is a central database for data that is collected and distributed to the standard units of the institution. Thus, this information can be accessed about activities across the organization or anywhere around the world, as well as when the information is entered into the system by one user; any information is updated accordingly. As shown in the screen (Figure1)

(Figure1)

(Al-Mashari, 2003) explained that the system's benefits (ERP systems) Are best achieved when the organization evaluates the performance measurement after implementing the system realistically. The benefits are administrative, operational, strategic, and robust infrastructure for information technology. The following table (Table 1) shows the benefits, which are divided into tangible and intangible benefits.

Tangible benefits realised	Intangible benefits realised
~ Inventory reduction	~ Information/visibility
~ Personnel reduction	~ New improved processes
~ Productivity improvements	~ Customer responsiveness
~ Order management improvements	~ Cost reduction
~ Financial close cycle reduction	~ Integration
~ IT cost reduction	~ Standardisation
~ Procurement cost reduction	~ Flexibility
~ Cash management improvement	~ Globalisation
~ Revenue/profit increases	~ Y2K
~ Transportation/logistics cost reductions	~ Business performance
~ Maintenance reductions	~ Supply/demand chain
~ On-time delivery	

(Table 1)

Implementation of ERP System

When implementing this system (ERP system), Within any institution, the concerned persons must consider that they will invest in it from the financial and non-financial sides (Al-Mashari, 2003). The financial aspect will include the costs of the licensed software equipment and the consultancy fee to transfer knowledge from the system provider to the user. The end-user will need to understand the system and manage the enterprise resource planning project because it is considered a project. Training is part of the financial side and includes the third side—time and money to implement the system (Whang, 2002). Without a correct understanding of ERP systems and proper support, there are stages of implementation. The project is subject to failure (Whang, 2002)

The proportion of the study that he conducted was about the evaluation and study of a small number of institutions that moved to ERP systems, which he arrived at for the reasons that led to the failure of the application. It turns out that the main reason is the Lack of suitable training plans for the system users. Also, it may be that the reason is that the institution does not have a clear goal to conform to business strategies. This project must receive special attention (Kansal, 2007). The Lack of understanding of the system and its capabilities (the ERP system) and the Lack of sufficient time To improve it radically to merge with the organization will lead to its failure. The merger is intended to merge operations.

Moreover, business tasks in the system to improve it drastically. Implementation indicates the system's success, but its improvement and maintenance are more significant evidence of its success.

1.Critical Failure Factors (CFDs)

1.1Pre-Implementation Phase

1.1.1Not Clear Strategic Visioning & Planning

Lack of a clear vision that could affect the project and its final results and Lack of a clear plan does not indicate the failure of the project, but it is a factor to be taken into consideration before starting the implementation of the ERP system, and it has been shown that the vague strategic goals and permanent change in the project goals and time are sub-factors that feed the idea of the plan And the unclear strategy

1.2 Implementation Phase

1.2.1Poor Change Management

When we talk about change management, we mean a change in the organization that is being dealt with many issues, such as organizational changes and stakeholder needs; it must be taken into account that the ERP system is a significant technical project that has a comprehensive impact on the organization and will lead to radical changes in it in terms of reports, employees and work processes. It was noted that by transferring this system, the services of some employees would be terminated as the services of The system would cover their tasks, so people avoid change. (Momoh, 2010) Resistance to change dramatically affects the project. Suppose it causes a delay in the progress of work. In that case, it is difficult to adapt to Employees, and there is no solution to this problem except education and correct communication with employees (Robbins, 2009). The organization's culture knows that every company has common standards among all employees, and these standards distinguish it from any other company and define the organization's culture. The culture of the hostile company is an aggressive culture that creates barriers for people to accept any change before them. Employees are one of the most critical factors in avoiding project failure (Robbins, 2009)

1.2.2 Lack of Communication

Communication that fails to inform employees about any change and not reporting them in any discussions of the benefits of the ERP system will lead to the team not accepting the system and the failure of the initiative and the project. Communication must be effective between all members of the organization, the team, and the end-user to ensure that all the systems' positives, standards, and procedures are explained and understood. Communication will lead to the failure of the project.

1.2.3ERP Strategy & Implementation Team

The absence of an ERP strategy may be the reason for the project's failure; a plan was explained to the employees to understand the mechanism of implementing the system and the strategy nutrients.

1.2.4 Poor Project Management

Effective project management is the basis for ensuring project success and Lacking the right skills. It will lead to the project's failure because it results from not defining the scope, not allocating enough time, and not estimating the correct cost. Control is an essential skill in managing any project. Failure to lead, plan and monitor the project can be the reason for the failure of the ERP project application (Nah, 2001).

Failure to give the system implementation sufficient time from the planning stage will lead to the project's failure. The project manager must ensure that the project schedule is proportional to its size (Nah, 2001)

1.2.5 Lack of Management Support &Involvement

We mean by supporting the higher management to support them for any problem during the project, including financial, moral, and political problems. Funds must be provided for the project not to stop it. Employees must be morally supported to feel that their efforts have been considered. The higher management must be present to resolve any dispute that may occur.

Lack of business management support may be a cause of project failure and mean a lack of understanding of the implications (Momoh, 2010)

1.3 Post-implementation

1.3.1 Poor testing

According to Garg (2010) (Garg, 2010), when the system is not tested before its operation, this will lead to the project's failure, as some processes may not be working correctly, so testing the project is very important.

3.1 Methodology

This research aims to evaluate the ERP implementation failure factors. This study adopted quantitative research to obtain helpful feedback from the RAK Government respondents by analyzing the questionnaires. Since the respondents of this survey represent the department's end-users, We hope to understand the respondents' honesty as possible to make the survey results more consistent with the ideas of most respondents rather than a qualitative survey of a few respondents. Therefore, the questions combine descriptive and self-explanation features, including single-choice, multiple-choice, and percentage options.

These choices were made so the ERP-SAP users could choose the options based on their actual experiences to the best answers that they could contribute. In this survey design, the respondents come from different Government entities. Each entity has different experiences of their ERP- SAP Implementation to have other concepts, especially the ERP failure percentage data. The data on this survey is significant in comparing research outcomes and guiding the analysis measures.

The task or decision on a project was mapping out which roles are involved in each task and at which level.

RACI matrix

A RACI matrix is a simple matrix used to assign roles and responsibilities to each.

The task or decision on a project was clearly mapping out which roles are involved in each project task and at which level.

RACI stands for Responsible, Accountable, Consulted,RACI stands for Responsible, Accountable, Consulted,and Informed. Each letter in the acronym represents a level of task responsibility.

Responsible	The "doers" of the work. Several people can be jointly responsible.
Accountable	This person is the "owner" of the work. He or she must sign off or approve when the task, objective, or decision is complete. This person must make sure that responsibilities are assigned in the matrix for all related activities. There is only one person accountable.
Consulted	These are the people who need to give input before the work can be done and signed off on. These people are "in the loop" and active participants. Try and minimize the number of consultants on the project as this will slow down decision-making and progress.
Informed	These people need to be kept "in the picture." They need updates on progress or decision, but they do not need to be formally consulted, nor do they contribute directly to the task or decision. Just be aware of having too many people in this column. The more people you have along for the ride, the more effort is communicating with them.

RACI					
Project:	FACTORS OF ERP IMPLEMENTATION FAILURE IN RAK GOVERNMENT			R	Responsible
Date:	30-4-2021			A	Accountable
				C	Consulted
				I	Informed
Project Deliverables	Maryam Alshehhi	Elena Laspona			
Introduction	R	R			
Statement of the Problem:	R	R			
Implication of the Study:	I	R			
Research Objectives	R	R			
Research Assumptions	R	R			
Methodology	R	R			
Results and Discussion:	I	R			
Literature Review	R	R			
Conclusion	R	I			

Research tools and tech

The survey is a process of gathering data that could involve a wide variety of data collection methods, including the questionnaire, defined as a systematic collection of questions. It is a powerful tool used to collect information from widely scattered sources. Surveys are usually used when one cannot communicate personally with everyone to seek responses. Moreover, it has various advantages like easy data analysis and visualization, scalability, and a quick way to get results.

Respondents in this survey included 36 specialists ERP SAP users from different RAK Government entities. The questionnaire includes information about risks associated with sustainable construction and covers three main sections. This survey aimed to obtain helpful feedback from the RAK Government respondents about ERP implementation failure factors.

RESULTS & ANALYSIS , MAIN BODY & CONCLUSION

4.1 Data Collection:

We used SurveyMonkey.com online platform to collect and analyze the survey questionnaire results. It has many templates for the users to edit and design questionnaires to fit their user's goals. It can directly type the questions on the appropriate template or upload them in word format, as shown in Appendix 1. In addition, it will automatically generate a link that the user can share or copy that will be sent to the specific respondents.

When the respondents complete the questionnaire, the platform will automatically record the information, like the source or time of filling. The questionnaire creator can check the situation of filling in real-time and snip the fundamental data analysis result.

From April 18 to April 27, 2021, we shared the questionnaire through WhatsApp, email, and M.S. Teams and received 36 valid data, as shown in appendix 2. The respondents were ERP SAP users from different RAK Government entities currently using an experienced ERP implementation on their assigned tasks.

4.2 Data Analysis:

The data analysis method used in this research is the statistical methods and charts, including bar charts and pie charts, to intuitively analyze and display the survey results. At the same time, We compared and analyzed the conclusions and evidence that led to the differences to improve the credibility of this research. Besides, we also analyze the correlation and logic between groups of questions because the survey data results of one question will support another conclusion from the side or explain reasons for the results of another conclusion. Indeed, it is also necessary to consult some pieces of literature review in this process. Finally, We will critically analyze the results of this survey, which will prove the significant value of this study and reflect on the limitations and future research directions of this paper.

4.3 Results and Discussion:

The result of the distributed survey questionnaire is being analyzed individually to have concrete data for evaluation.

Figure one shows that out of 36 respondents in the survey, the majority were ERP-SAP users. Ten of them were heads of the department. The percentage of the respondents who strongly agreed was 40%, agreed 45%, undecided 4%, and disagreed with statement 3%. Therefore, based on the data result, most of the respondents in the RAK Government agree that senior management vision and support helped them achieve the ERP implementation goal.

Figure 1: Management support and vision to achieve ERP implementation goal

Figure2: ERP implementation fits the RAK Government nature itself.

Based on the 36 respondents, 95% and only 5% disagree that the ERP system matches the essential nature of the company, as shown below's the pie chart.

Figure3: In the planning stage of the data, the company first sets goals and objective and consider the feedback from all department entities personnel involved in the implementation.

Was the company set goals and strategy and to take into consideration the feedback from all departments government entities and personnel involved?

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
Yes	86.11% 31
No	13.89% 5
TOTAL	36

Figure 3 data result in shows that 86% said that the company considers the feedback and the idea of each department personnel involved before implementation. Moreover, 14% disagree with the statement that maybe their ideas and feedback were not considered. That is why on the next figure #4, there are some reasons why the RAK Government ERP-SAP implementation failed in some areas.

Figure 4: Concrete reasons from the ERP-user's perspective why RAK Government implementation failed in some areas

As per my Analysis, the results of the implementation failure below results showed that even if the senior management supported and created a plan with the SAP users. It is not easy to measure and compare the planning stage to the implementation stage of the actual implementation plan. Figure 4 shows that the 36 respondents majority issues with ERP implementation were first the **UNCLEAR CONCEPT OF NATURE AND USE OF ERP SYSTEMFOR THE USERS PERSPECTIVE**, which is almost 70%, 25 select this factor based on their experienced, second **USERS RESISTANCE TO CHANGE** 50%, 18 respondents believe that most of the failure factors were the users not coordinating correctly and not even supporting the plan of the senior management. The third was **TOO TIGHT PROJECT SCHEDULE**. Around 38% of the respondents believed that the system's project scheduling accomplishment was so tight that the implementation was not as successful as expected. The 4th, fifth, and sixth factors were **POOR IT INFRASTRUCTURE** 25%, **POOR PROJECT MANAGEMENT EFFECTIVENESS** 19%, and **POOR SENIOR MANAGEMENT SUPPORT** 19%.

Reasons of ERP implementation failure:

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
▼ Poor IT Infrastructure and Consultant effectiveness	25.00% 9
▼ Too tight project schedule	27.78% 10
▼ Unclear concept of the nature and use of ERP system for the user's perspective	69.44% 25
▼ Poor senior management support	19.44% 7
▼ User's resistance to change	50.00% 18
▼ Poor project management effectiveness	19.44% 7

Figure5: To measure the objectives implementation achievement, the figure below shows that majority of the respondents believed that 80% of the RAK Government ERP implementation was achieved from the 64% (23) responses, followed by 60% achievements from 33% (12) responses, then only one respondent believed that 100% was achieved.

What percentage of implementation objectives were achieved?
(Objectives such as Integrating/streamlining business processes, information sharing, improving productivity etc.)

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
▼ 100%	2.78% 1
▼ 80%	63.89% 23
▼ 60%	33.33% 11
▼ 40%	0.00% 0
▼ 20%	0.00% 0

Figure 6: The functionality of the ERP Implementation being used by the ERP users.

Figure 6 illustrated that majority of the respondents confirmed that 80% of the functionality was being used in the 17 responses (47%), followed by 60% from the 11 respondents (31%), then followed 40% (3 responses). Two respondents believed that 100% were being used.

How much functionality of your ERP systems has been used? (System functionalities such as streamline operations, integrating functions, managing resources, information exchange etc.)

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
-	5.56% 2
100%	5.56% 2
80%	47.22% 17
60%	30.56% 11
40%	8.33% 3

Figure7: Data migration failure rate compared to the previous system

As per the pie chart below, it is clear that most respondents believed that the data migration failed from less than 50% to less than 25%.

What was the failure rate of Data Migration (from the previous system to ERP system)?

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

ANSWER CHOICES	RESPONSES
100%	2.78% 1
75%	11.11% 4
50%	13.89% 5
Less than 50%	33.33% 12
Less than 25%	39.89% 14

4.4 Main Body of the Paper:

Based on the data results and the Analysis, the RAK Government ERP-SAP implementation failure factors were mainly on the Unclear concept of the nature and use of the ERP system from the user's perspective and the users' resistance to change. So it is clearly understood that the main reasons for the issue were with the **USERS**. It could be that the users do not cooperate with the senior managers or the users' skills are not capable of doing the tasks, especially in maintaining and configuring the specific reports needed.

Moreover, other reasons not stated in the survey were the training, which is the central aspect of the successful implementation. The other data survey results received that the senior management set goals and objectives in coordination with the SAP users. Yes, the respondents believed that the senior management set goals, then the questions are: are they communicating it to the End-Users properly? Did the End-users fully understand the system implementation's aim and benefits? Moreover, the managers checked first if the end-users skills and capacity to handle the role of the project were enough. So it should not be only setting goals and objectives for the project. It should be pre-implementation checking as per the literature review stated and monitoring the milestone of the system's progress. Then, if there is some revision to the needs, they can update it. Another survey data result was the achievement of the implementation; the majority of the respondents believed that the implementation was successful. Based on the survey, we asked respondents from different RAK Government entities for additional management support, training, and implementation processes. In some entities, the ERP implementation went well, and until now, it has worked well and served its purpose. Still, some entities are not maximizing the functionality of the ERP system because of the Users' resistance to change.

4.5 Conclusion

It has been concluded that the investigation of the factors that can contribute towards the ERP implementation of the RAK government showed a critical review in the report. It has been seen that the failure is due to several reasons that define vague concepts of the nature and use of ERP systems for the user's perspective and for the user's resistance to change and commitment to the services with the governmental factors. The factors are seen as defining a Lack of communication with the end-users. The inefficient training processes define the poor management of the project services. The government of RAK is recommended to use strategies to manage the country's failure and identify the services using the most effective oil management. The unity defines internal fraud that can use a Lack of coherence management and applying the parties. The inefficient services are based on the Analysis that can define coherence management of the ERP implementation and organizational failures. The factors are considered as managing efficient roles in the failure of the ERP implementation. The suggestions are used for identifying the management and considering greater accountability of the management towards the direct management of the responsible failure of the project management.

Moreover, based on the facts and the results of the survey and the Analysis, we strongly recommend the senior management of the RAK Government, if any ERP implementation in the future, to:

1. Communicate effectively with the ERP- USERS any impact related to their work, how the system will improve their task, and why it is essential to their work and the government.
2. The ERP users and the managers should be committed to the system's timeframe, scheduled plan, and objectives.
3. The senior management should check the capability of the personnel assigned to the specific tasks to see if they can handle them effectively and efficiently.
4. Proper training should be done by the personnel's specific system access, roles, or assignment.

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Appendices:

Appendix1

Factors of ERP/ SAP Implementation Failure in RAK Government Survey

Guidance Notes:

This questionnaire is based on respondents' experience from one complete ERP (**Enterprise Resource Planning**) system implementation (SAP). This has been designed to study the factor of ERP failure during implementation in RAK Government.

The findings of this study will assist in developing a simulation model for ERP implementation actions that will enhance the implementation experience for improvement.

This survey will apply the following definitions:

- a. Number of days spent on factors including planning, implementation, and training;
- b. Senior management support may involve: providing overall support to the implementation, setting goals, and developing strategy.

1. Senior management's vision and support helped you to achieve the implementation goal.

- Strongly Agree
- Agree
- Undecided
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

2. Was the implementation of the system fit the company nature itself?

- Yes

No

3. How long did it take to complete ERP implementation (days/months)?

4. Did the company set goals and strategy and consider the feedback from all departments, government entities, and personnel involved?

Yes

No

5. Reasons for ERP implementation failure:

Poor IT Infrastructure and Consultant effectiveness

Too tight project schedule

Unclear concept of the nature and use of ERP system for the user's perspective

Poor senior management support

User's resistance to change

Poor project management effectiveness

6. What percentage of implementation objectives were achieved? (Objectives include integrating/streamlining business processes, sharing information, improving productivity, etc.)

100%

80%

60%

40%

20%

0%

7. Based on your response to the above question, please state how much each Failure Factor below contributed to your answer above.

Management Support _____

Project Management _____

Data/Infrastructure _____

Users _____

I.T. Support _____

8. How much functionality of your ERP systems has been used?

(System functionalities include streamlining operations, integrating functions, managing resources, information exchange, etc.)

100%

80%

60%

40%

20%

0%

9. Based on the response to the above question, please state how much each failure contributed to your answer above.

Management Support _____

Project Management _____

Data/Infrastructure_____

Users_____

IT Support_____

10. What was the failure rate of Data Migration (from the previous system to the ERP system)?

- 100%
- 75%
- 50%
- Less than 50%
- Less than 25%

Thank you for your valuable time in completing this questionnaire. If you have any comments or suggestions, please contact Maryam Al Shehhi and Ma. Elena Laspona on maelena.laspona@aurak.ac.ae; maryamal.alshehhi@aurak.ac.ae

Appendix 2 Responses volume from April 21- April 27

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